

USING TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

Zakirova Madina Shavkat qizi

University of World Languages of Uzbekistan

**Department of English Language Teaching Methods
and Educational Technologies teacher**

Abstract. Nowadays, the use of innovative technologies in education has become mandatory and necessary. This article examines the benefits of using innovative technologies during the lesson, students' approach to education, and the impact of using innovative technologies on students' learning.

Key word. Education, innovative technologies, interactive method, interactive, nuance, teaching process, teaching methods.

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi kunda ta'limda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish shart va zarur bo'lib qolgan. Ushbu maqolada dars jarayonida innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning foydali tomonlari, o'quvchilarning ta'limga yondashuvi, innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanganda o'quvchilarning bilim olishiga ta'siri o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'z. Ta'lim, innovatsion texnologiyalar, interfaol metod, interaktiv , nuans, dars jarayoni, o'qitish metodlari.

Аннотация. В настоящее время использование инновационных технологий в образовании стало обязательным и необходимым. В данной статье рассматриваются преимущества использования инновационных технологий на уроке, подход учащихся к образованию, а также влияние использования инновационных технологий на обучение учащихся.

Ключевое слово. Образование, инновационные технологии, интерактивный метод, интерактив, нюанс, учебный процесс, методы обучения.

Introduction.

Nowadays, when development around the world is rapidly increasing, education also requires technological changes. Changes have opened up wide opportunities for teachers to integrate technology-supported materials into teaching and learning practice through the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). The introduction of innovative technologies into educational practice has helped students improve their approach to the lesson, increase their level of knowledge, and make the teaching process easier and more interesting for teachers. When teaching through innovative technologies, students develop their imagination, learn to think quickly and act quickly.

Innovation means introducing innovations. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and interactive methods are mainly used to implement them. Interactive methods are collective thinking, that is, a way for teachers to influence students. In interactive methods, teachers and educators work together, students become participants, not just listeners, no student is left out of the lesson. Such a process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- forcing the student to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, create and search;
- ensuring that students have a constant interest in knowledge during the learning process;
- strengthening the student's interest in knowledge in an independent manner with a creative approach to each issue;
- organizing the constant joint activities of the teacher and student.

The integration of technology and innovation in teaching and learning refers to the use of technology to facilitate learning through a variety of media, create opportunities for student-centered learning, engage and differentiate students, and provide learning benefits (Fullan, 2011; Ertmer et al., 2012). The use of technology in teaching includes

activities such as lesson planning, lecture presentation, writing, research, and peer collaboration (Bebell et al., 2004). In addition, the use of technology as a learning tool places students, rather than teachers, at the center of the learning process, while also focusing on social interactions and connections across domains.

From the research conducted, we can see that as a result of the integration of educational technologies, the development of students' abilities and leadership support have developed. The integration of innovative education and educational technologies is: the use of presentation technologies, assessment and feedback, access to and exchange of information.

Conclusion. Each sector in society is interconnected. The development of the education sector is of great importance for the development of society. By using innovative technologies in education and introducing interactive methods in teaching students, it is possible to provide society with highly educated personnel. We can see this from the experience of many countries. In particular, in Uzbekistan, we can see that the level of knowledge and leadership qualities of students have developed. That is why much attention is currently being paid to the education sector. By introducing new innovative technologies into the education sector, we can achieve the set goals even faster.

References.

- 1.Elizabeth Landaa, Chang Zhua, Jennifer Sesabo. Readiness for integration of innovative teaching and learning technologies: An analysis of meso-micro variables in Tanzanian higher education. InternationalJournal of Educational Research Open. 2023
2. Ishmukhamedov R.J. Ways to improve educational efficiency with the help of innovative technologies. T.: TDPU, 2004.
3. Yunusovna, S. Z. The Role of the Conversational Implicative in Linguopragmatics on the Basis of Formal and Informal Letters. TDO'TAU, 2022

4. Sayibova Z. Y. The role of innovative technologies in the field of education. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. 2023